

INNOVATIVE WAYS TO TEACH ENGLISH

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Abdullayeva Mavluda

Asaka District School No. 56

Today, foreign language skills are becoming an integral part of professional education. At the initial stage, important attention is paid to pronunciation. Harmer noted that the first requirement from native speakers during a conversation is pronunciation. At the beginning of the learning process, the teacher should focus on the pronunciation of the student. Although grammar and vocabulary are considered the main thing, if the speaker's pronunciation is irregular, then this is all useless. Native speakers can also understand speech with grammatical errors if the speaker pronounces the words Round.3 therefore, when teaching, the main emphasis is first placed on pronunciation. In doing so, benefiting from the various audios of native speakers gives a good result. The teacher should teach how to pronounce letters, words Round during the lesson. As such, at the initial stage, great attention is paid to oral speech and the cultivation of reading techniques. If we consider in this regard the types of speech activities of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to carry out the following tasks when teaching them:

- a) generating a reading mechanism;
- b) growing oral reading techniques;
- c) teaching to understand what he studied .

In the primary stage, a broad place is given to the type of reading, mainly aloud. The texts reserved for reading are also the simplest and gradually more complex than the simplest. But it must be said that despite the fact that the work activity in the initial stages is mainly focused on the development of oral skills, it is not able to solve the issue of growing oral speech in English. He only goes through the preparatory stage to work on real oral speech. In addition, reading words beautifully and fluently increases the reader's love for learning this language.

In addition pupils are in the primary stage of the Present indefinite Tense., The low indefinite Tense. , Are required to be well versed in verb tenses such as the Future indefinite Tense and to be able to use verb forms vividly in these tenses.

Using question and answer exercises, the results of strengthening the student's speech, improving his memory, repetition are achieved. New words that come out of the texts are memorized. As a result of Q & A, the repetition of those words in memory and the skills to be able to apply in speech are formed. In addition, the organization of various games in classes increases the pace of learning, increasing the student's interest in language learning. In the game " Hot ball", readers take a circle, shooting the ball with one of the new words to each other. Participants are eliminated from the

game without repeating what each other has said, repeating, or halting without being able to say a word. This way the game is continued.

In the middle stage, grammar is taught in depth relative to the first stage, according to the mentioned grammatical rules, students are given exercises, tests, and their knowledge is tested. independent work at the stage plays a special role, especially with a foreign language. At this stage, the requirements for the lesson differ from those in previous skirts. Now the lesson is not seen on the basis of oral speech, since at this stage most of the language material is passively studied (without prescription). That is, reading will play a key role.4 textures are also large in size, and the language material is complex. Reading, speaking, listening exercises are constantly interrupted. When organizing a lesson, reading is assigned a separate day, speaking a separate day, listening a separate day. The tasks assigned to the House are also structured more and more complex than the previous stages. In Speaking lessons, a 2-minute speech is prescribed, throwing a topic in the middle. Another method is to distribute cards with text themes to readers. Each reader has their own feedback on the subject given on the card of their choice.

Adequate attention should be paid to the formation of speech skills and the development of social flexibility in trainings carried out in the educational process. In addition, the success of each lesson in education largely depends on the correct Organization of training. The lesson should be based on the creative cooperation of the teacher and the student. Only then can students think independently freely, their will is brought up.

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